

β -cyclodextrin polymer as tetrodotoxins scavenger in oyster extracts

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ABSTRACT

Tetrodotoxins (TTXs) are potent marine neurotoxins involved in poisoning cases in humans after consumption of some marine organisms. A cell-based assay (CBA) providing toxicological information is a commonly used method for their detection because of its high sensitivity. However, matrix effects may interfere in the CBA. In this work, five insoluble cyclodextrin polymers, with different chemical structures (β CDP-14-DS2, β CDP-13-DS2, β CDP-13-DS4, β CDP-14-DS4 and β CDP-N-DS5) have been investigated as novel clean-up materials for oyster extracts containing TTXs. The best recoveries have been achieved with β CDP-14-DS2 (~100%), which allowed exposing cells to 27-fold higher oyster matrix concentrations and decreased the LOQ down to 46 μ g equiv. TTX/kg. Then, the applicability of this strategy has been demonstrated with oyster extracts from The Netherlands and comparing the results with immunoassay and liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). This clean-up strategy combined with CBA could be implemented for TTXs detection in monitoring programs to ensure seafood safety.

1. Introduction

Tetrodotoxin (TTX) is one of the most lethal naturally occurring neurotoxins in the marine environment [1]. TTX was initially thought to be present only in certain pufferfish species. However, it has been later reported in a taxonomically diverse range of marine and terrestrial organisms [2]. The bacterial origin of TTX is today widely supported due to the growing number of bacterial species, such as *Pseudomonas* sp., *Vibrio* sp., and *Alteromonas* sp., reported to have the capability to produce the toxin. In addition, marine environmental parameters, such as seawater pH and temperature, are among the most important triggers of events leading to TTX accumulation in European bivalve molluscs. Seawater pH plays a remarkable role, as it positively influences the accumulation of TTX in both oysters and mussels, while temperatures above 15 °C trigger the etiological agent responsible for TTX production [3,4]. Despite significant research in this area, the contribution of microorganisms to TTX bioaccumulation in marine ecosystems is still not

fully clear [5].

TTX is a water-soluble molecule with a low molecular weight. To date, more than 30 TTX analogues have been described, with varying toxic potencies [6]. Structurally, TTX ($C_{11}H_{17}O_8N_3$) and its analogues are aminoperhydroxyquinazoline derivatives that exist as dipolar ions. TTX consists of only one positively charged guanidinium group and the cation is stabilized by resonance effect. Therefore, TTX has a unique heterocyclic structure [7]. TTX and its analogues are known to selectively block the voltage-gated sodium channels (VSGCs, also known as Na_v), reducing the influx of sodium into the cell and, consequently, leading to acute health effects in animals and humans [8].

Until 2007, TTX had never been considered as a potential threat in European waters. However, in the last few years, tetrodotoxination incidents have been encountered in Europe, including Mediterranean countries. After the first record of human intoxication due to TTX ingestion caused by a *Charonia lampas lampas* trumpet shell, concerns about TTX as a food safety hazard in Europe have been raised [9]. In EU

Abbreviations: TTX, tetrodotoxin; VSGC, Nav, voltage-gated sodium channel; EFSA, European Food Safety Authority; CONTAM, Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain; MBA, mouse bioassay; LC-MS/MS, liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry; CBA, cell-based assay; O, ouabain; V, veratridine; CD, cyclodextrin; ¹H NMR, Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance; FTIR, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy; ESEM, Environmental Scanning Electron Microscopy.

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no legislation for TTX in bivalves is established. However, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM) conducted a risk assessment and concluded that a concentration of 44 μg TTX/kg of shellfish meat, as regards marine bivalves and gastropods, is not expected to lead to adverse effects in humans [10]. This value is adopted in Dutch and Belgian national legislation for the monitoring of shellfish production areas. Additionally, Dutch and Belgian experts have proposed a higher value of 110 μg TTX equiv./kg [11], based on the EFSA report [10] and in vitro study results [12]. Nevertheless, more evidence-based information is needed regarding TTX toxicity.

Traditionally, the mouse bioassay (MBA) was the most widely applied test for the assessment of marine toxins, including TTX. However, this method suffers from ethical concerns and not suitable for obtaining quantitative data. Therefore, alternatives were accepted or are undergoing validation testing. Immunochemical assays and biosensors based on antibodies have recently emerged as new tools for the detection of TTX in natural samples. They are highly sensitive and easy to implement. However, their measurement is based on a structural information and, therefore, they do not provide estimations of the toxicity of a sample [13,14]. Instrumental analysis techniques, such as LC-MS/MS, were one of the first analytical methods developed for TTX detection and is now routinely used. These techniques can identify and quantify with high accuracy and specificity the toxin of purpose, but are expensive and complex, and require reference materials to know the retention times and fragmentation patterns of the different toxins of the same family [15].

Cell-based assays (CBAs) are promising alternatives to MBAs for the detection of marine toxins. These assays have multiple advantages, including the reduction of animals used, the potential detection of unknown marine toxins and the global toxicological response that they provide. Based on the mode of action of VGSC toxins, the CBA with Neuro-2a cells was initially developed to detect VGSCs blockers, such as TTXs [16]. These marine toxins have no cytotoxic effect on Neuro-2a cells, and their detection requires the addition of ouabain (O), a Na^+/K^+ -ATPase inhibitor, together with veratridine (V), which induces permanent activation of the VGSCs [17]. Under this O/V treatment, sodium influx results in the cellular swelling and subsequent death of Neuro-2a cells [16]. Following the addition of TTX, an increase of cell viability is observed as this toxin counteracts the effect of O/V. The Neuro-2a CBA is very sensitive and can be applied in the detection of TTX in shellfish. However, its application may be hampered by the sensitivity of living cells and compounds from the shellfish meat matrix that may affect the Neuro-2a cell viability regardless the presence of O/V [18]. These limitations affect the limit of quantification (LOQ) and may also lead to false results. A possible solution to reduce these undesirable shellfish matrix effects is to clean up samples to obtain purified extracts, less prone to cause interferences. The possibility to expose cells to higher concentrations of these cleaned-up extracts enables to detect a lower TTX concentration.

Cyclodextrins (CDs) are cyclic oligosaccharides, formed by α -1,4-linked glucose units, with a hydrophilic outer surface and a lipophilic central cavity [19]. Among them, α -, β - and γ -CDs are the most common types, which are composed of 6, 7, and 8 glucose units, respectively. The truncated cone-shaped CDs possess a hollow, tapered cavity of 0.79 nm in depth, while both the top and bottom diameters increase with the number of glucose units [20]. The multifunctional characteristics of CDs have enabled to use them in different fields, such as drug delivery [21], biosensing [22], as passive sampling materials for lipophilic marine toxins [23] and to clean-up fish extracts to detect ciguatoxins with CBA [24]. In this work, five insoluble β -CD polymers, with different chemical structures ($\beta\text{CDP-13-DS2}$, $\beta\text{CDP-14-DS2}$, $\beta\text{CDP-13-DS4}$, $\beta\text{CDP-14-DS4}$ and $\beta\text{CDP-N-DS5}$) have been used as novel clean-up materials of shellfish extracts before their analysis with a CBA for the detection of TTXs. First, the capacity of the CD polymers to capture TTX was tested in solvent. Once the best CD polymer was chosen, its ability to capture TTX

in the presence of shellfish matrix was tested. Then, the ability of this CD polymer to decrease or even remove the shellfish matrix effects was evaluated. Afterwards, recovery values from spiked negative shellfish extracts were calculated. Finally, naturally contaminated shellfish were cleaned up and analysed, and results were compared with those obtained with LC-MS/MS analysis and a magnetic bead-based immunoassay.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents and materials

Glacial acetic acid (HAc) was obtained from Chemlab (Zedelgem, Belgium). Acetonitrile (MeCN) was purchased from Fisher Scientific (Loughborough, UK). Formic acid (98–100 %) and ammonia (25 %) were purchased from VWR (Amsterdam, the Netherlands). Acetonitrile (Ultra LC-MS), methanol (Ultra LC-MS), and water (Ultra LC-MS) were purchased from Actua-All (Oss, the Netherlands). Heptafluorobutyric acid (HFBA) (98 %) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, the Netherlands). Ultrapure Milli-Q water (18.2 M Ω /cm) was used to prepare the solutions (Millipore Iberica Ltd., Madrid, Spain). TTX standard was purchased from Abcam plc (Cambridge, UK) and the standard solution was prepared at 1 mg/mL in 1 % HAc. Neuroblastoma murine (Neuro-2a) cells were purchased from ATCC/LGC standards (Manassas, VA, USA). Foetal bovine serum (FBS), ouabain (O), veratridine (V), phosphate buffered saline (PBS), penicillin–streptomycin, RPMI-1640 medium, sodium pyruvate, thiazolyl blue tetrazolium bromide (MTT) were purchased from Merck KGaA (Gernsheim, Germany). Anti-TTX monoclonal antibody (Mab) was obtained from Deltaclon (Madrid, Spain).

2.2. Synthesis and characterisation of cyclodextrin polymers

Insoluble anionic polymers ($\beta\text{CDP-13-DS2}$, $\beta\text{CDP-14-DS2}$, $\beta\text{CDP-13-DS4}$, $\beta\text{CDP-14-DS4}$) (Fig. 1a): βCD (12 g, 10 mmol) was dissolved in 10 mL of 12 % NaOH and stirred for 15 min. The corresponding sultone (1,3-propane or 1,4-butane sultone) was then slowly added (20 mmol or 40 mmol) and the mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. The crude products were precipitated in cold acetone (500 mL) and washed thoroughly with acetone. The resulting materials were then redissolved in 33 % NaOH and a 7-fold molar excess of epichlorohydrin was added dropwise. Stirring was maintained for 1 h at 60 °C, followed by precipitation over ethanol (1 L) and filtration. The crude products were purified by overnight Soxhlet extraction in refluxing ethanol, followed by refluxing with water for another 2 h to rehydrate the polymer network to give a white powder that was grinded and sieved at 40 Mesh (8–9 g, final yield). This procedure afforded a set of four insoluble polymers varying in the spacer length of the attached sulfonate group (denoted $\beta\text{CDP-13...}$ and $\beta\text{CDP-14...}$) and degrees of substitution ~ 2 and ~ 4 (denoted ...-DS2 and ...-DS4).

Insoluble cationic polymer ($\beta\text{CDP-N-DS5}$) (Fig. 1b): βCD (12 g, 10 mmol) was dissolved in 30 mL of 33 % NaOH and stirred for 15 min, followed by the portionwise addition of 2,3-epoxypropyl-trimethylammonium chloride (9 g, 60 mmol). The mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature and a 7-fold molar excess of epichlorohydrin was then added dropwise. Stirring was maintained for 1 h at 60 °C, followed by precipitation over ethanol (1 L) and filtration. The crude product was purified by overnight Soxhlet extraction in refluxing ethanol and water to give a white powder (6.5 g) that was grinded and sieved at 40 Mesh.

Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (^1H NMR) spectra were recorded in D_2O at 400 MHz in a Bruker Avance Neo 400 spectrometer at 298.15 K. All signals were referenced to internal HDO. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra (Attenuated Total Reflection mode) were measured in a Jasco FT/IR-6700 Infrared spectrometer at room temperature. The samples were dried overnight under vacuum over P_4O_{10} before analysis. Powder X-ray diffractograms were recorded

Fig. 1. Synthetic procedure for the preparation of (a) anionic and (b) cationic β CD polymers. Broken lines indicate that the polymer structure extends in all directions from the CD monomer.

on a Bruker-AXS D8-Discover diffractometer equipped with a vertical θ - θ goniometer using Cu K α radiation (1.5406 Å) in the 2θ range of 2 to 50°. Environmental scanning electron microscopy (ESEM) was recorded in a Quanta 600 microscope (FEI Company, Inc.) under high vacuum at 25 kV. Samples were analyzed at a 10-mm working distance.

2.3. Shellfish sample extraction and clean-up

Oyster samples were obtained from shellfish production sites in the Netherlands in 2022. Oyster extracts to be analysed with the CBA and the immunoassay were obtained according to the protocol described in Campàs et al. [13], which was based on the EURLMB protocol developed for the interlaboratory validation of HILIC-LC-MS/MS for TTX in mussels [25], with slight modifications [26]. Briefly, 1 g \pm 0.1 g of shucked oyster homogenate was weighed into a 15-mL tube and 1 mL of 1 % HAC was added. After shaking the tube at 2,500 rpm for 5 min on a multi-tube vortex mixer, the sample was placed in a boiling water bath set at 100 °C for 10 min. The tube was cooled and shaken again at 2,500 rpm for 5 min. Finally, the sample was centrifuged at 4,500 rpm for 10 min, and the supernatant was passed through a 0.2 μ m nylon filter and kept at –20 °C until analysis. The resulting extracts contained oyster matrix at a concentration of 1,000 mg oyster tissue equiv./mL. Oyster extracts to be analysed with LC-MS/MS were obtained according to a similar protocol, with slight differences: 2 g \pm 0.1 g of shucked oyster homogenate in 3 mL of 1 % HAC in MeOH, sonication bath for 15 min, centrifugation at 3,600 rpm for 5 min, and adjustment of the volume to 4 mL with H₂O.

For the clean-up, four insoluble anionic CD polymers (β CDP-13-DS2, β CDP-14-DS2, β CDP-13-DS4 and β CDP-14-DS4) and one insoluble cationic CD polymer (β CDP-N-DS5) (negative control) were tested. The protocol was similar to that described in Campàs et al. [24] with some modifications. Briefly, 50 mg of each cyclodextrin polymer were introduced into Eppendorf tubes. For the activation, cyclodextrin polymers were incubated for 30 min with 1 mL of 20 % MeCN and 1 % HAC,

centrifuged for 15 min, rinsed with 1 mL of Milli-Q H₂O, centrifuged for 15 min, incubated for 30 min with 1 mL of 1 % HAC and centrifuged for 15 min. Then, 1 mL of TTX standard solution at 200 ng/mL (800, 400, 100, 50, 25 and 12.5 ng TTX/mL in the characterisation) in 1 % HAC or oyster extract at 1,000 mg oyster tissue equiv./mL in 1 % HAC was added and incubated overnight. After 24 h, samples were centrifuged for 15 min and the supernatant was discarded; a washing step was performed adding 1 mL of Milli-Q H₂O, mixing, centrifuging for 15 min and removing the supernatant, which was discarded. For the TTX elution, two consecutive extractions were performed. For each one, 1 mL of 20 % MeCN and 1 % HAC was added and incubated for 2 h, and samples were centrifuged for 15 min. Both supernatants were transferred to a vial and pooled together. Therefore, a final volume of 2 mL was obtained. Incubation steps were performed under agitation on a mixing wheel. All centrifugation steps were performed at 15,000 rpm on an Eppendorf microcentrifuge 5424R.

2.4. Cell maintenance and cell-based assay

Neuro-2a cells were maintained in RPMI-1640 medium (which supplemented with 10 % FBS, 1 % penicillin–streptomycin and 1 % sodium pyruvate) in an incubator (BINDER GmbH, Tuttlingen, Germany) at 37 °C in 5 % CO₂ humid atmosphere. The CBA was performed as previously described [27]. Briefly, Neuro-2a cells were trypsinized and suspended in culture medium (containing 5 % FBS). Then, Neuro-2a cells were seeded in a 96-well microplate at an approximate density of 35,000 cells/well in 200 μ L of culture medium for 24 h at 37 °C in 5 % CO₂ humid atmosphere. Prior to exposure to TTX standard solution or oyster extract, some Neuro-2a cells were pretreated with 20 μ L of a mixture containing O and V at final concentrations of 0.125 and 0.2 mM in PBS, respectively. TTX standard solutions or oyster extracts were dried under an N₂ stream at 40 °C using a TurboVap evaporator, reconstituted in RPMI medium, serially diluted, and 10 μ L was added to

the wells with and without O/V pretreatment (final concentrations in the wells were 100, 33.3, 11.1, 3.70, 1.23, 0.41, 0.14 and 0.05 ng/mL for TTX or 217.4, 72.5, 24.2, 8.05, 2.68, 0.89, 0.30 and 0.10 mg oyster tissue equiv./mL for oyster extracts). After 24 h, cell viability was measured using the MTT assay. Absorbance at 570 nm was measured with a Synergy LX microplate reader from BioTek (Agilent Technologies, Inc., Santa Clara, CA, USA). Measurements were performed in triplicate. Calibration curve for TTX in the presence of O/V was constructed and fitted to a sigmoidal logistic four-parameters equation:

$$y = y_0 + \frac{a}{1 + \left(\frac{x}{x_0}\right)^b}$$

Where a and y_0 are the asymptotic maximum and minimum values respectively, x_0 is the x value at the inflection point and b is the slope at the inflection point.

2.5. Immunoassay

The magnetic bead (MB)-based colorimetric immunoassay protocol is described in a previous publication [13]. Briefly, 10 μ L of maleimide-activated MBs were transferred to a 1-mL tube and rinsed three times and 1 mL of 1 mM cysteamine in binding buffer (0.1 M PBS, 10 mM EDTA, pH 7.2) was added and incubated for 2 h at room temperature. After washing, 1 mL of TTX solution (25 μ g/mL) in binding buffer containing 10 % v/v formaldehyde was added and incubated overnight at 4 °C. The TTX-coated MBs were rinsed and resuspended in 1 mL of binding buffer. For the competition, 200 μ L of the TTX-coated MBs were transferred to a 0.5-mL tube, the supernatant was removed and 100 μ L of the TTX standard solution or shellfish extract and 100 μ L of anti-TTX mAb at 1/2000 dilution in 1 % w/v BSA-binding buffer were added and incubated for 30 min at room temperature. After washing, 200 μ L of 1/1000 IgG-HRP dilution in 1 % w/v BSA-binding buffer was incubated for 30 min at room temperature. For colour development, 50 μ L of rinsed immunocomplex was transferred to a new 0.5-mL tube and after supernatant removal, 125 μ L of TMB liquid substrate was added and incubated for 10 min, and 100 μ L of TMB liquid substrate was collected for colorimetric measurement at 620 nm in a microtiter plate. All incubation steps were performed under agitation. Measurements were performed in triplicate. The immunoassay calibration curves were also fitted using the sigmoidal logistic four parameter equation.

2.6. Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) analysis

The standard addition method was applied to the LC-MS/MS analysis. Samples were fortified with 60 μ g/kg TTX standard. When samples exceeded the level of 60 μ g TTX/kg, a higher level of standard addition was applied. When samples exceeded the level of 250 μ g TTX/kg, they were diluted with blank shellfish extract of the same species.

Chromatographic separation of TTX was achieved on a ZORBAX bonus RP RRHD 2.1 x 100 mm, 1.8 μ m (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Mobile phase A consisted of 35 mM HFBA in water, and mobile phase B consisted of 35 mM HFBA in 80 % v/v acetonitrile. The injection volume was set at 2 μ L. The column temperature was set at 40 °C and the total run time was 10 min. The gradient elution with a flow of 0.2 mL/min was as follows: 2 min at 100 % mobile phase A, then linearly increased to 100 % mobile phase B in 3 min and kept at 100 % mobile phase B for 3 min. Subsequently, the gradient went back to 100 % mobile phase A in 0.1 min and kept at 10 % mobile phase B for 1.9 min to equilibrate the LC column for the next run.

For LC-MS/MS analyses, a Waters Acquity UPLC coupled to a Waters Xevo TQ-S tandem mass spectrometer (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) was used. The triple quadrupole MS system was operated in positive electrospray mode and data were recorded in multiple-reaction-monitoring

(MRM) mode using two ion transitions per toxin: 5,6,11-trideoxyTTX: m/z 272.1 > 254.1 (collision energy (CE) 20 eV) and m/z 272.1 > 162.2 (CE 38 eV); 11-norTTX-6-ol: m/z 290.1 > 272.1 (CE 20 eV) and m/z 290.1 > 162.1 (CE 38 eV); 4,9-anhydroTTX: m/z 302.1 > 256.1 (CE 20 eV) and m/z 302.1 > 162.1 (CE 38 eV); 5-deoxyTTX and 11-deoxyTTX: m/z 304.1 > 286.1 (CE 20 eV) and m/z 304.1 > 176.1 (CE 38 eV); TTX and 4-epiTTX: m/z 320.1 > 284.1 (CE 30 eV) and m/z 320.1 > 162.1 (CE 38 eV). Furthermore, a cone voltage of 40 V, a capillary voltage of 0.5 kV, source temperature of 150 °C, desolvation temperature of 600 °C and desolvation gas flow of 1000 L/h was set. Quantification of TTX analogues was performed against TTX, assuming equimolar responses, given the equivalent structural fragmentation in MRM transitions.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthesis and characterization of the CD polymers

The anionic polymers were prepared using a two-step strategy. Native β CD was first treated with NaOH followed by addition of the corresponding cyclic sulfonate ester precursors (1,3-propane and 1,4-butane sultones, respectively). Two different CD:sultone molar ratios were used (1:2 and 1:4) to obtain a series of alkylsulfonate esters of β CD having 1,3-propyl and 1,4-butyl spacers, respectively. A portion of these materials was analysed by 1 H NMR to determine the degree of substitution of alkylsulfonate groups (Fig. 2a). Integration of the methylene groups of the substituents with respect to the anomeric protons of the β CD core resulted in all cases in a degree of substitution essentially identical to the initial molar ratios employed in the synthesis, indicating a stoichiometric incorporation of the alkylsulfonate groups (see tables in Fig. 1). The final insoluble polymers were obtained by crosslinking with epichlorohydrin at a 1:7 M ratio in strongly alkaline solution.

Fig. 2b and 2c show the FTIR spectrum and powder x-ray diffractogram of β CDP-14-DS2. The infrared spectrum shows the characteristic intense bands at 3360 cm^{-1} and \sim 2900 cm^{-1} due to O-H and C-H stretching vibrations. The main difference with respect to native β CD is visible in the region of 1400–1000 cm^{-1} with a peak corresponding to S = O stretching and a more intense C-O peak at 1032 cm^{-1} due to the presence of the bridging HC-OH groups. The x-ray diffraction pattern of this polymer (Fig. 2c) showed two broad peaks at 5°, 12° and 18° (2 θ), in sharp contrast with the diffractogram obtained for β CD and confirming its amorphous and polydisperse characteristics. Finally, analysis by ESEM of this material (Fig. 2d) showed a compact and rough surface, consistent with the high degree of crosslinking present on the insoluble polymer.

3.2. Tetrodotoxin recovery from cyclodextrin polymers in solvent

The ability of the different CD polymers to capture TTX was evaluated using TTX standard in 1 % HAC. Fig. 3 shows the TTX contents obtained in the eluates expressed as recovery percentages. Because of the cationic charge of TTX at acidic pH, the cationic β CDP-N-DS5 was used as a negative control. As expected, recovery value obtained with the negative control for the toxin was very low and close to zero, 4 %. TTX recovery obtained with β CDP-14-DS2 was excellent (100 %). However, the recovery value obtained with β CDP-13-DS2 was lower (31 %) and those obtained with β CDP-14-DS4 and β CDP-13-DS4 were not appropriate for our purpose (14 % and 8 %, respectively). Although these polymers are highly cross-linked and polydisperse materials, these differences could be explained considering that the low substitution degree of β CDP-13-DS2 and β CDP-14-DS2 exert less steric hindrance to the interaction of TTX with the β CD cavities. Similarly, the longer C4 spacer between the sulfonate group and the CD backbone in β CDP-14-DS2 could accommodate better the TTX molecule. Since β CDP-14-DS2 showed the best capture efficiency, this polymer was chosen for subsequent experiments.

The maximum amount of TTX that can be captured by β CDP-14-DS2

Fig. 2. (a) ¹H NMR spectrum (400 MHz, D₂O) of the soluble precursor of the synthesis of βCDP-14-DS2, (b) FTIR spectrum, (c) powder x-ray diffractogram and (d) ESEM image of βCDP-14-DS2.

Fig. 3. Recovery percentages obtained with the five CD polymers in the spiking of TTX in solvent.

was then evaluated. Fig. 4 shows the amounts of TTX obtained per mg of βCDP-14-DS2 when it was incubated with different TTX concentrations. When spiking concentrations lower than 200 ng TTX/mL, 100 % of recovery was achieved. However, TTX concentrations higher than 200 ng/mL resulted in a decrease of the toxin recovery values, being 65 % and 48 % for 400 and 800 ng/mL, respectively. The maximum amount captured by the CD was 35 ng TTX/mg CD. If higher TTX concentrations had been spiked, recovery values could have probably decreased even more, but higher amounts could have been attained. Apart from the capture capability, it is important to consider that the volumes and equilibrium rates may certainly playing a role in the amount of captured toxin.

3.3. Evaluation of oyster matrix effects

As we explained before, in CBAs for the detection of neurotoxins such as TTX, the pre-treatment of cells with O/V, which induces permanent activation of VGSCs, is necessary. Under this O/V treatment, sodium influx causes the swelling and subsequent death of Neuro-2a cells.

Fig. 4. Amount of TTX captured by βCDP-14-DS2 when spiking different TTX concentrations in solvent.

Following the addition of TTX, the cell viability increases, as this toxin counteracts the toxic effect of O/V. In the absence of O/V pre-treatment, no cytotoxic effect should be observed. However, when analysing natural samples, non-specific cytotoxicity may be observed due to the presence of compounds from the sample matrix. This interference in the CBA has also been observed with other neurotoxins such as CTX [28]. Although less common, these matrix compounds can also interfere with the cells pre-treated with O/V, increasing the cell viability regardless of the toxin contents. In CBAs for the detection of VGSC openers (e.g., CTX and PbTX), the required O/V concentrations decrease cell viability to 80 %, and this effect is barely observed. On the contrary, in CBAs for VGSC blockers (e.g., TTX), the O/V concentrations used are higher in order to decrease cell viability to 20 % and, subsequently, detect the rescuing effect of this toxin. This more drastic pre-treatment makes the assay more susceptible to suffer from non-specific cell viability increases at high matrix concentrations [29]. Therefore, the ability of the selected CD to remove both types of interferences (without and with O/V pre-treatment) was evaluated.

Cells with and without O/V pre-treatment were exposed to TTX-free

oyster (samples 23-EX-152 and 23-EX-153 in Table 1) crude extracts and extracts that had undergone the clean-up process (Fig. 5). In the absence of O/V, the oyster crude extracts significantly reduced the cell viability below 90 % when matrix concentrations were 2.68 mg oyster tissue equiv./mL or higher (No CD / No OV). Nevertheless, the clean-up with β CDP-14-DS2 decreased this matrix effect in the CBA, as no cell mortality was observed up to 217.4 mg oyster tissue equiv./mL (100 % cell viability was achieved) (CD / No OV). In the presence of O/V, the TTX-free oyster crude extracts at 0.30 mg oyster tissue equiv./mL did not affect the assay performance, but higher concentrations increased the cell viability up to a certain matrix concentration (No CD / OV), where the cell viability decreased again due to interferences observed in the absence of O/V. In the case of the cleaned-up oyster extracts, this non-specific increase in cell viability (above 10 %) started at 24.2 mg oyster tissue equiv./mL and therefore was not noticed at 8.05 mg oyster tissue equiv./mL. The clean-up strategy with β CDP-14-DS2 allowed exposing cells to 27-fold higher oyster matrix concentrations compared to crude extract (arrows A and B in Fig. 5). Considering the IC₂₀ to be 0.37 ng TTX/mL, the calculated LOQ of the assay with no clean-up is 1,233 μ g equiv. TTX/kg. Nevertheless, the implementation of the clean-up step with the CD polymer decreases the LOQ down to 46 μ g equiv. TTX/kg, very close to the value proposed by EFSA (44 μ g equiv. TTX/kg) [10] and lower than the safe level of 110 μ g equiv. TTX/kg proposed by Dutch and Belgian experts [11,12].

3.4. Recovery from spiked oyster extracts

After achieving a good recovery in solvent and observing the removal of oyster matrix effects at concentrations up to 8.05 mg oyster tissue equiv./mL, the performance of the β CDP-14-DS2 was then evaluated by spiking a TTX-negative oyster extract with different TTX concentrations and proceeding with the clean-up. The recovery values were a bit higher than expected, being 115 %, 110 %, 125 %, 131 % and 132 % for 800, 400, 200, 100 and 50 μ g TTX/kg of shellfish tissue, respectively. Although the oyster matrix concentration had been proved to not interfere with the controls without and with O/V, these high recovery values seem to indicate that the presence of oyster matrix compounds could interfere with the TTX quantification with CBA. In fact, some studies [30–32] attributed the interferences observed in a CBA to the competition between VGSCs blockers and monovalent and divalent cations such as Li⁺, Cd²⁺, Ca²⁺, and Zn²⁺. Turner and co-workers [33] also demonstrated that high concentrations of metals, including zinc and manganese, present in oyster samples compete with VGSCs blockers for the binding to Na_v channels. Considering that the clean-up strategy developed in this work aims to detect the presence of TTX in shellfish,

this overestimation of the toxin content is not a drawback. In fact, in an official monitoring programme, the CBA would be able to avoid false negative results and identify the positive ones, which should be subsequently analysed by LC-MS/MS to be confirmed. In any case, further work would be necessary to remove this possible interference. Nevertheless, these recovery values can be applied in the determination of TTX contents in naturally contaminated samples.

3.5. Analysis of naturally contaminated shellfish

Oyster extracts obtained from the Netherlands were cleaned-up with β CDP-14-DS2 and analysed with CBA. To demonstrate the applicability of our method to the determination of TTX contents in naturally contaminated samples, results of CBA were compared to these extracts were also analysed using two different approaches. Table 1 shows the results of TTX equivalent contents provided by CBA after the application of the recovery values, the contents provided by immunoassay and the LC-MS/MS quantification of some TTX analogues and the total sums, values resulting after application of the toxicity equivalency factors (TEFs) to the individual LC-MS/MS quantifications (multiplication of the LC-MS/MS values by the corresponding TEFs obtained by CBA) [27]. The TEFs were 0.011 and 0.404 for 5,6,11-trideoxyTTX and 11-norTTX, respectively. The presence of TTXs by CBA was detected in 10 out of the 15 samples. From a quantitative point of view, in the positive samples, TTX concentrations ranged from 47 μ g/kg to 960 μ g/kg. The immunoassay, having a lower LOQ, showed presence of TTXs in 13 out of the 15 samples, and in these samples, the TTX concentrations ranged from 10 μ g/kg to 639 μ g/kg. LC-MS/MS analysis detected TTXs in 13 out of the 15 samples. TTX and 5,6,11-trideoxyTTX were detected in almost all positive samples, whereas 11-norTTX was present in only 4 of them (chromatograms of sample 23-EX-148 are shown as an example in Fig. 1S of Supplementary material). In this case, the TTX equivalent concentrations ranged from 39 μ g/kg to 800 μ g/kg. Although in some samples 5,6,11-trideoxyTTX was found at relevant concentrations, its low toxicity makes its contribution to the very small. On the contrary, 11-norTTX is contributing to a higher extent to the global response in the 4 samples where it is present. A remarkable result is the high concentration of TTXs found in some of these oyster extracts, which not only exceed the EFSA safety level of TTX in shellfish meat, but even reach ~20-fold higher contents. These concentrations represent a potentially high risk from a food safety perspective.

Good correlations between techniques were observed, although, in general, the CBA slightly overestimated the TTX contents compared to the immunoassay (Fig. 6a) and LC-MS/MS analysis (Fig. 6b). These differences between techniques in the analysis of shellfish extracts are

Table 1

Tetrodotoxin (TTX) contents in naturally contaminated oysters determined by CBA after the β CDP-14-DS2 clean-up step and applying the recovery value (μ g TTX equiv./kg), immunoassay (μ g TTX equiv./kg) and by LC-MS/MS (μ g TTX/kg).

Sample code	CBA	Immunoassay	LC-MS/MS			
			TTX	5,6,11-trideoxyTTX	11-norTTX	Σ LC-MS/MS
23-EX-180	92	122	123	35	<LOQ	123
23-EX-179	960	639	797	363	<LOQ	800
23-EX-178	<LOQ	57	58	22	164	125
23-EX-177	313	152	171	23	<LOQ	171
23-EX-172	47	64	70	11	<LOQ	70
23-EX-169	74	113	138	24	<LOQ	138
23-EX-162	413	275	332	224	<LOQ	334
23-EX-154	70	33	39	13	<LOQ	39
23-EX-153	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
23-EX-152	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
23-EX-148	193	62	86	43	82	120
23-EX-146	73	117	132	84	<LOQ	133
23-EX-145	<LOQ	19	26	31	135	81
23-EX-143	<LOQ	10	<LOQ	19	184	86
23-EX-141	102	33	50	13	<LOQ	50

CBA: LOQ = 46 μ g TTX equiv./kg; Immunoassay: LOQ = 1 μ g TTX equiv./kg; LC-MS/MS: LOQ = 20 μ g TTX/kg.

Fig. 5. Cell viability for two TTX-free oyster extracts without and with β CDP-14-DS2 clean-up. **A:** concentration required for the analysis of cleaned-up extract. **B:** concentration required for the analysis of crude extract.

Fig. 6. Linear regressions for the correlations between TTX quantifications by CBA and immunoassay (a) and by CBA and LC-MS/MS analysis (b).

not surprising and have also been observed in other studies [29,34]. When comparing TTX values obtained with different techniques, it is necessary to take into account their detection principle. The CBA provides a global toxicological response from TTX, TTX analogues and/or some other toxins that may exist in the sample and have the same mechanism of action as TTX. The immunoassay also provides a global response, although in this case it is not toxicological but structural, which originates from all TTX and TTX analogues that cross-react with the anti-TTX MAb. This cross-reactivity can differ between the different analogues and may be related to their toxicity or not. Depending on their concentration in the sample and their cross-reactivity with the TTX antibody, TTX analogues would contribute to a greater or lesser TTX equivalent contents [35]. On the other side, LC-MS/MS analysis, although also based on a structural detection, is able to determine individual TTX and TTX analogue contents. If TEFs of TTX analogues are available, they can be applied to the individual quantifications to provide a composite toxicological estimation. However, if some of them are either not known or not targeted in the analysis, or if their TEFs have not been previously determined, instrumental analysis methods may not properly estimate the toxicity of the sample. If the analysis does not consider these toxic TTX analogues, or if the applied TEFs are lower than the real ones, the toxicity of the sample will be underestimated. If the TEFs applied are higher than the real ones, the toxicity will be overestimated.

The TTX underestimation by LC-MS/MS and the immunoassay in relation to the CBA seems to be probably due to the presence of unknown TTX analogues that may exist in the samples (which have not been detected by LC-MS/MS and/or do not cross react with the antibody) and could be responsible for the disagreement between approaches. Furthermore, the fact that samples were not extracted with the same extraction protocol and at the same moment may lead to discrepancies in the quantification of TTX equivalent contents of a sample. Many

authors [29,36] highlighted the importance of the extraction method that should be applied in the analysis of shellfish extracts and the unspecific effects of solvent and its interferences in the assay. Additionally, as mentioned before, other studies [32,33] explained the differences between CBA and other techniques by the presence of some other components toxic to the cells such as metal ions and/or fatty acids, which may be responsible for an overestimation of the toxicity by the CBA. Despite these discrepancies between detection methods, the use of β CDP-14-DS2 as a clean-up material has been demonstrated to remove the oyster matrix effects, attain good TTX recovery values and provide 27-fold higher sensitivities in the CBA.

Finally, compared to other clean-up materials, cyclodextrins have the advantages of being cheap and ecologically sustainable. Additionally, they can be rationally synthesized to capture different types of toxins thanks to their chemical and structural versatility, which could be of interest for other applications.

4. Conclusions

β -cyclodextrin polymers have been tested as new and sustainable clean-up materials to purify TTXs from European shellfish that are going to be analysed with CBA. The best results, in terms of matrix effect removal and recovery of TTXs, have been obtained with β CDP-14-DS2 (100%). The presence of a longer C4 spacer between the sulfonate group and the CD backbone could play a crucial role in enhancing the capture of TTX. The removal of matrix effects with this sustainable material was evident, making possible to expose cells to oyster matrix concentrations at 8.05 mg oyster tissue equiv./mL. Additionally, the implementation of the clean-up step with the CD polymer has decreased the LOQ down to 46 μ g equiv. TTX/kg, very close to the value proposed by EFSA (44 μ g equiv. TTX/kg) and lower than the safe level of 110 μ g equiv. TTX/kg proposed by Dutch and Belgian experts. We have demonstrated that our

clean-up strategy provides 27-fold higher sensitivities to the CBA for TTX detection in shellfish. This is an excellent achievement considering the extremely low TTX contents that need to be detected to guarantee shellfish safety and protect human health. Therefore, this clean-up step can be easily implemented in the protocol for the detection of TTXs with CBA, allowing the detection of this toxin at low concentrations. This is an excellent achievement considering the toxic potential of TTX to human health, being a food safety hazard in Europe.

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Mounira Alkassar: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Jaume Reverté:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Alex Frago:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Mabel Torrén:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Mirjam Klijnstra:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Arjen Gerssen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Jorge Diogène:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Mònica Campàs:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.microc.2024.110585>.

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